

REGIONAL FACTOR ANALYSIS IN IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF MEAT CATTLE PRODUCTION SYSTEMS

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Abstract. This article examines the assessment of the effectiveness of regional factors in the development of beef cattle breeding. The study analyzes the impact of natural and climatic conditions, feed base, infrastructure level, production resources, and market factors on the development of the sector. In addition, the level of development of beef cattle breeding across regions is evaluated using economic and statistical methods, and scientifically grounded proposals and recommendations for improving efficiency are developed.

Keywords: beef cattle breeding, regional factors, efficiency, feed base, infrastructure, economic analysis, resource utilization, livestock development.

The procedure for calculating production and sales costs of products (works and services) and their classification is carried out in accordance with the requirements of the Regulation approved by Resolution No. 54 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 5 February 1999 [4]. This cost accounting system was initially introduced on an experimental basis in 1995, and since 1999 it has been widely implemented in practice.

According to financial and economic reports on agricultural producers in Uzbekistan's agro-industrial complex, at the end of 2022 the production cost of 1 ton of live-weight cattle meat amounted to 5,763 thousand UZS, while the average selling price was 6,820 thousand UZS. However, during the period from 2018 to 2022, the share of high-quality beef produced from cattle decreased by 0.96%, from 75.27% to 74.31%.

In agricultural organizations, only in the Syrdarya Region, annual losses from the sale of cattle meat exceed 2.5 billion UZS, while at the national level total sectoral losses reach 45–50 billion UZS (according to data from the Federal State Budgetary Institution "Center for Expert Evaluation of Efficiency in the Agro-Industrial Complex"). These trends indicate the need to develop measures aimed at improving the economic efficiency of meat production in the Syrdarya Region.

The intensive development of livestock farming in the Republic of Uzbekistan is only possible through a consistent intensification process, which includes a significant increase in the production of high-energy feed, improvement of its quality indicators, enhancement of feeding levels, and improvement of balanced diets enriched with additives, minerals, vitamins, and proteins. The production of

high-quality beef also requires substantial investment in breeding and genetic improvement programs. The comprehensive implementation of the above measures is feasible primarily on the basis of agricultural organizations.

At the same time, the efficiency of raising and fattening cattle of dairy and dual-purpose breeds remains relatively low compared to other livestock sectors.

In most agricultural organizations of the Syrdarya Region, the increase in live weight of dairy cattle is characterized by losses, which reduces the overall profitability of livestock farming.

The main reason for the low profitability of poultry meat production is the increase in electricity tariffs, which constitute a significant share of production costs. The profit generated from cost savings per unit of production due to productivity growth in poultry farming is largely used to cover rising energy costs and expenses for grain feed.

Beef cattle production for slaughter remains unprofitable; however, the level of losses has decreased by 3.1 percentage points over the past five years due to a faster increase in selling prices compared to production costs.

In the Syrdarya Region, one of the largest cattle herds in the country is raised, numbering approximately 186,204 heads.

An analysis of the financial reports of several livestock enterprises operating in the region shows that most farms operate with chronic losses. Without strict government support measures, this sector is likely to remain persistently unprofitable. Table 1 presents the financial results of cattle meat production and sales in agricultural organizations of the Syrdarya Region for the period 2021–2025.

Table 1

Efficiency of production and sale of livestock products in agricultural organizations of the Syrdarya region

Indicator	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Profitability (+), loss (-) from the sale of livestock products %,	-6,7 28,7	-10,1 -30,1	-9,1 -31,5	-8,1 -30,2	-9,0 -31,3

According to the results of the analysis, every 1 UZS spent on beef production generates a loss of more than 30 tiyin for agricultural producers.

The causes of sectoral unprofitability lie in a complex system of factors, primarily low productivity. According to our calculations, instead of 200 kg of live weight per head, productivity should be approximately 2.5 times higher. As a

result, livestock fattening remains a highly cost-intensive activity across the entire sector (Table 2).

An analysis of fattening efficiency in the context of agricultural producers in certain regions demonstrates that it is possible to achieve not only break-even but also efficient expanded production. Thus, among the 15 agricultural organizations engaged in cattle fattening in the Syrdarya Region, only 4 enterprises are able to cover production costs; however, their profits are not sufficient to compensate for the overall losses of fattening enterprises in the region as a whole.

The implementation of the key provisions of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Food Security” is only possible with simultaneous support for agricultural producers engaged in non-marginal activities. Such measures include increasing the share of state support in proportion to the sector’s contribution to gross agricultural output, providing tax incentives, strengthening material and technical infrastructure, and improving labor productivity through the introduction of digital technologies combined with state support mechanisms.

Table 2.

Production of beef in the Syrdarya region and its production efficiency

Indicator	2021 y	2022 y	2023 y	2024 y	2025 y	Growth rate,%
Average annual stock of young cattle, thousand heads.	0,96	1,13	0,96	1,37	1,59	164,93
Production of young cattle meat, thousand tons	2,07	2,41	2,11	2,99	3,71	179,69
Produced per 1 head, kg	198,00	195,00	210,00	206,00	211,00	106,57
Storage costs, million soums.	26 589,92	31 229,13	27 633,75	39 800,10	49 610,75	186,58
Cost of 1 kg of meat sold, thousand soums.	100,55	108,63	115,89	132,07	155,81	154,95
Selling price for 1 kg of meat, thousand soums	80,00	85,00	90,00	105,00	120,00	150,00

Meat production profitability (+), harmfulness (-), %	-	-	-	-	-	-	112,45
	20,44	21,76	22,34	20,50	22,98		

To assess the degree and nature of the relationship between cattle meat productivity and its determining factors, a correlation-regression analysis was conducted by solving multiple correlation problems. For this purpose, six multifactor correlation-regression models were developed for the year 2026.

The first model covers agricultural organizations in the Boyovut District (1 unit).

The second model covers agricultural organizations in the Oqoltin District (2 units).

The third model covers agricultural organizations in the Sayxunobod District (5 units).

The fourth model covers agricultural organizations in the Sirdaryo District (2 units).

The fifth model covers agricultural organizations in the Xovos District (2 units).

In these models, dependent (y) and independent (x) variables were identified. Multiple correlation-regression analysis makes it possible to evaluate the impact of each factor included in the model on the studied dependent indicator under the condition of other factors being constant, as well as in any combination with a given level of accuracy. An important condition in this case is the absence of functional dependence between the factors.

In economic processes, dependent variables include indicators that directly or indirectly reflect production performance results. Accordingly, in these correlation models, the indicator characterizing the level of meat productivity of animals during fattening and rearing is considered the dependent variable. The factor variables, in turn, reflect their degree of influence on the production process.

The variables used in the model are as follows: **y** – average annual live weight gain of 1 head of cattle during fattening, c; **x1** – livestock density per 100 ha of pasture land, heads; **x2** – animal load per herder, heads; **x3** – cost of keeping 1 head, thousand UZS; **x4** – labor costs per 1 head, person-hours; **x5** – labor intensity of producing 1 centner of beef, person-hours.

The evaluation of solution parameters consists of comparing obtained results with standard statistical criteria. If the parameters meet the standards, the

interpretation of results is carried out. Otherwise, the model is corrected by eliminating observations with gross (anomalous) errors and by excluding or replacing factor variables. Using the adjusted model, a new solution is obtained, and its parameters are also evaluated.

Parameter estimation begins with the analysis of the multiple correlation coefficient (R), which determines the strength of the linear relationship between the dependent variable (y) and multiple independent variables. The coefficient ranges from 0 to 1, and the closer it is to 1, the stronger the relationship.

For a number of farms in the Boyovut District, the results showed a very strong relationship between the dependent and factor variables, confirmed by the multiple correlation coefficient (R = 0.949).

The multiple correlation coefficient is characterized by the error of the correlation coefficient (Or = 0.017) and its reliability (Tr = 55.930). These values confirm a strong relationship between the dependent and factor variables and indicate a high level of reliability of the model.

The variability of the dependent variable (y) is explained by the combined influence of selected factors (x1, x2) by 56.630%. In particular, changes in the average annual live weight gain of cattle are explained by 12.912% due to variations in the cost of maintaining 1 head, and by 9.191% due to labor productivity.

Economic research is generally characterized by a relatively high level of variance. Therefore, in practice, a dispersion level of up to 50–60% is considered acceptable. In this case, the variability coefficients reflect a normal distribution (maximum coefficient of variation $Y_{x1} = 57.178\%$), and therefore the correlation-regression model does not require further adjustment.

Table 3.

Results of multi-factor correlation and regression analysis of the economic activity of agricultural enterprises in the Bayaut district of the Syrdarya region for 2025

Indicators	Y	X1	X2	X3	X4	X5
Error in correlation coefficients	0,017	0,167	0,164	0,120	0,138	0,165
Reliability of correlation coefficients	55,930	-0,614	-1,038	4,514	3,104	-0,961
Arithmetic mean	2,025	13,894	63,632	26,956	40,092	20,112
Standard quadratic deviations	0,539	7,944	25,156	11,563	18,429	7,329

Coefficients of variation, %	26,629	57,178	39,533	42,898	45,966	36,444
Regression coefficients	2,100	0,007	-0,001	0,008	0,041	-0,097
Beta coefficients		0,108	-0,060	0,172	1,398	-1,319
Coefficients of determination, %	89,967	1,056	2,900	29,192	18,350	2,508
Specific detection factors	89,967	-1,112	1,025	9,277	59,894	20,883
Multiple correlation coefficient	0,949					
Parity correlation coefficients	Y	-0,103	-0,170	0,540	0,428	-0,158
	X1		-0,121	-0,059	-0,162	-0,014
	X2			0,014	-0,369	-0,316
	X3				0,435	0,176
	X4					0,796

The parity correlation coefficient - r_2 - is a parameter that reflects the closeness (strength) of the relationship between the individual factor and the resulting factor.

Absolute values of R_{yxj} reflect the following binding strength:

$ry_{xj} = 0$ - the absence of a connection;

$0.00 < ry_{xj} < 0.20$ - insignificant, unreliable dependence;

$0.20 < 0.40$ - weak connection;

$0.40 \leq rx_j < 0.60$ - average dependence;

$0.60 \leq 0.80$ - strong bond;

$0.80 \leq rx_j < 1.00$ - very strong bond.

The greatest impact on the level of meat productivity of animals is associated with factors such as expenditures for the maintenance of 1 head and labor costs per 1 head. The closeness of the relationship between x_3 and y , and between x_4 and y , determined by pairwise correlation coefficients, is direct; at $t=4.514$, the average is $ry_{x3}=0.540$; at $ry_{x4}=0.428$, $t=3.104$). A weak and inverse relationship is observed between meat productivity and the level of animal density for rearing and feeding, the animal load per livestock breeder, and the labor density of products intended for the rearing and feeding of cattle ($rx_1 = -0.614$ at $t = -1.103$, $rx_2 = -0.170$ at $t = -1.038$, and $rx_3 = -0.158$ at $t = -0.961$). It follows that the presented correlation-regression model requires adjustments to a number of factors based on the reliability values of the paired correlation coefficients.

Table 4.

Results of solving the multi-factor correlation-regression model for the economic activities of agricultural enterprises in the Akaltyn district of the Syrdarya region for 2025

Indicators	Y	X1	X2	X3	X4	X5
Error in correlation coefficients	0,058	0,130	0,133	0,116	0,133	0,121
Reliability of correlation coefficients	12,984	1,200	0,477	3,088	0,355	-2,498
Arithmetic mean	2,217	27,772	94,238	29,357	35,984	16,899
Standard quadratic deviations	0,560	13,130	50,289	9,418	21,058	12,137
Coefficients of variation, %	25,263	47,278	53,363	32,080	58,522	71,821
Regression coefficients	1,606	0,001	0,003	0,006	0,036	-0,068
Beta coefficients	-	0,033	0,226	0,101	1,364	-1,471
Coefficients of determination, %	6,630	2,449	0,402	12,912	0,224	9,191
Specific detection factors	56,630	0,520	1,434	3,625	6,452	44,597
Multiple correlation coefficient	0,753					
Parity correlation coefficients	Y	0,156	0,063	0,359	0,047	-0,303
	X1	-	0,133	-0,271	-0,231	-0,296
	X2	-	-	-0,197	-0,198	-0,083
	X3	-	-	-	0,241	0,011
	X4	-	-	-	-	0,876

Assessment of the parameters for solving the multi-correlation problem according to the above criteria indicates that it requires correction. To this end, it is necessary to exclude the characteristics of three factors (x1, x2, x5) from the correlation-regression model. In this case, the composition of indicators in the new, corrected model will be as follows (Table 5).

Table 5.

Results of solving the multifactorial correlation-regression model of the economic activity of agricultural enterprises in the Bayaut district of the Syrdarya region for 2025

Indicators	Y	X1	X2
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Error in correlation coefficients	0,112	0,120	0,138
Reliability of correlation coefficients	5,197	4,514	3,104
Arithmetic mean	2,025	26,956	40,092
Standard quadratic deviations	0,539	11,563	8,429
Coefficients of variation, %	26,629	42,898	45,966
Regression coefficients	1,196	0,020	0,007
Beta coefficients		0,437	0,239
Coefficients of determination, %	33,808	29,192	18,350
Specific detection factors	33,808	23,588	10,219
Multiple correlation coefficient	0,581		
Parity correlation coefficients	Y	0,540	0,428
	X1		0,435
	X2		

According to the results of the analysis of the two-factor model, the correlation between the selected resulting and factor indicators in the correlation model is moderate and weak, which is confirmed by the numerical value of the multiple correlation coefficient ($R = 0.581$). At the same time, the error of the correlation coefficient ($OR=0.112$) and the reliability of the correlation coefficient $TR=5.197$ confirm the presence of a moderate correlation between the resulting and factor indicators, indicating sufficient reliability of the multiple correlation coefficient.

The interpretation of the analysis results includes the study of regression coefficients, determination coefficients, and individual determination coefficients.

The coefficients of the regression equation are the coefficients of the regression relationship:

$$y = 1.196 + 0.020x_1 + 0.007x_2$$

u - average annual increase in live weight of cattle during growth and fattening, 1 head, st.;

x_1 - maintenance costs for 1 head, thousand soums;

x_2 - labor costs, per person/hour per head. If we replace the arithmetic mean values of the factor indicator - x_1 , x_2 - in the equation, the calculated value of the resulting factor - Y - will also be the arithmetic mean.

The parameters of the linear regression equation for a factor indicator show how the average value of the resulting indicator changes as a result of a one-unit change in the factor indicator.

That is, if the average annual cost of maintaining 1 head is increased by 100,000 soums, then the average annual increase in live weight of cattle during the feeding and growth period will increase by 0.020 c. If labor costs per head are increased by 1 person/hour, the average annual productivity of the cattle increases by 0.007 c.

Standardized regression coefficients or beta coefficients - B_j are used to determine the factors that have the most significant impact on the resulting factor.

With multilinear relationships, each beta coefficient characterizes the degree to which a specific factor influences the outcome, taking into account the interdependence of all factors.

Beta coefficients take values from -1 to +1 and reflect an inverse or direct relationship depending on the sign. The strength of the relationship between the factor and the resulting indicators is determined by comparing the absolute values of the beta coefficients.

In our case, the greatest absolute value is the beta coefficient of the factor indicator x_3 - $B_2 = 0.172$. This means that among the factors included in the model, factor indicator x_3 (financial costs for feeding 1 head of livestock) is the primary one, containing the largest reserves for increasing the profitability level of livestock farming.

The square of the correlation coefficient is called the coefficient of determination. The multiple determination coefficient (DMD) indicates how the change in the result depends on the change in all factors included in the correlation-regression model.

In our case, the coefficient of determination (DMD = 33.808%) indicates that the variability of the resulting characteristic is 33.808% due to fluctuations in the factor properties (x_1, x_2) included in the correlation-regression model.

Often, a separate definition coefficient - K_{yxj} is used to determine the percentage dependence of each factor in a correlation-regression model. If a paired coefficient of determination indicates the degree of influence of one factor on the result without considering other factors, then a separate coefficient of determination reflects this influence. Overall, the factors of the correlation-regression model affect livestock productivity by 33.808%, including 23.588% due to x_1 and 10.219% due to x_2 , respectively.

The results of solving the multi-correlation problem for the total number of agricultural organizations in other districts of the Syrdarya region were performed in a similar manner.

After adjusting for parameters such as the reliability of pair correlation coefficients ($tyx_1=1.200$; $tyx_2=0.477$; $tyx_3=3.088$; $tyx_4=0.355$; $tyx_5=-2.498$), variability coefficients, and the interfactor coefficient of pair correlation ($rx_4x_5=0.876$), the following factors are preserved in the correlation-regression model:

u - average annual increase in live weight per 1 head of cattle during the growing and feeding period, centners;

x1 - expenditure of funds for the maintenance of 1 head, thousand soums.

x2 - labor costs for feeding and raising 1 centner of livestock, person/hour

Table 6.

Results of the analysis of the multi-factor correlation-regression model of the economic activity of agricultural enterprises in the Akaltyn district of the Syrdarya region for 2025

Indicators	Y	X1	X2
Error in correlation coefficients	0,112	0,120	0,138
Reliability of correlation coefficients	5,197	4,514	3,104
Arithmetic mean	2,025	26,956	40,092
Standard quadratic deviations	0,539	11,563	18,429
Coefficients of variation, %	26,629	42,898	45,966
Regression coefficients	1,196	0,020	0,007
Beta coefficients		0,437	0,239
Coefficients of determination, %	33,808	29,192	18,350
Specific detection factors	33,808	23,588	10,219
Multiple correlation coefficient	0,581		
Parity correlation coefficients	Y	0,540	0,428
	X1		0,435
	X2		

The correlation density between the selected factors and the average annual increase in live weight during the growth and feeding periods of the animals is slightly lower than in the first statistical set, but nonetheless moderate and weak ($P = 0.4733$). The error of the multiple correlation coefficient ($Or=0.058$) and the reliability of the multiple correlation coefficient ($Tr=12.984$) confirm the presence of a moderate correlation between the resulting and factor indicators, indicating sufficient reliability of the multiple correlation coefficient.

The regression equation of the second correlation model has the following form (Table 6):

$$y = 1.824 + 0.022x_1 - 0.014x_2$$

The regression coefficient at x_1 shows that if the average annual cost of maintaining 1 head is increased by 100,000 soums, the average annual increase in live weight of the cattle increases by 0.022 c.

The regression coefficient in X_2 characterizes the possibility of increasing the meat productivity of cattle by reducing labor costs or, in other words, increasing labor productivity. If the labor costs per 1 t of product are reduced by 1 man-hour, the average annual increase in live weight of the cattle increases by 9,191 c.

The variability of the resulting factor (y) is associated with the combined influence of the selected factors (x_1, x_2) by 84.995%, including an average annual increase in live weight of cattle by 24.447% due to changes in maintenance costs per head, and by 29.622% due to labor productivity.

Table 7.

Results of solving a multi-factor correlation-regression model of the economic activity of agricultural enterprises in the Saykhunabad district of the Syrdarya region for 2025

Indicators	Y	X1	X2	X3	X4	X5
Error in correlation coefficients	0,027	0,173	0,169	0,134	0,175	0,124
Reliability of correlation coefficients	34,757	-0,845	-1,249	3,702	0,562	-4,375
Arithmetic mean	1,332	25,878	120,170	15,489	0,016	0,013
Standard quadratic deviations	0,476	26,303	116,102	6,760	0,008	0,008
Coefficients of variation, %	35,718	101,639	96,615	43,644	50,398	56,600
Regression coefficients	1,409	-0,001	-0,001	0,017	44,525	-71,256
Beta coefficients		-0,030	-0,153	0,239	0,752	-1,140
Coefficients of determination, %	84,995	2,135	4,454	24,447	0,970	29,622
Specific detection factors	84,995	0,437	3,239	11,840	7,409	62,071
Multiple correlation coefficient	0,922					
Parity correlation coefficients	Y	-0,146	-0,211	0,494	0,098	-0,544
	X1		-0,050	-0,219	-0,022	0,048

	X2			-0,031	-0,268	-0,131
	X3				0,537	0,141
	X4					0,723

The presence of several industrial enterprises on the territory of the small industrial zone in the "Farovon" mahalla of the Saykhunabad district, as well as the cotton-textile cluster "Sirdaryo-Politex" LLC in the district, is a limiting factor in terms of qualified involvement in animal husbandry.

One of the main factors for this region is labor productivity in meat farming. According to the results of 2025, the average monthly salary of livestock workers was one of the lowest in the republic, averaging 1,450 thousand soums.

Table 8.

Results of the analysis of the multi-factor correlation and regression model for the economic activities of agricultural enterprises in the Syrdarya district of the Syrdarya region for 2025

Indicators	Y	X1	X2	X3	X4	X5
Error in correlation coefficients	0,045	0,140	0,138	0,087	0,104	0,141
Reliability of correlation coefficients	18,376	-0,723	-1,068	7,117	4,995	-0,243
Arithmetic mean	1,169	19,179	165,230	16,200	16,017	0,014
Standard quadratic deviations	0,459	15,316	158,994	8,681	0,012	0,007
Coefficients of variation, %	39,288	79,860	96,226	53,584	72,409	51,267
Regression coefficients	0,967	0,000	0,000	0,015	35,339	-46,451
Beta coefficients		0,006	0,057	0,292	0,937	-0,751
Coefficients of determination, %	68,217	1,024	2,184	38,419	26,765	0,117
Specific detection factors	68,217	-0,060	-0,838	18,078	48,464	2,573
Multiple correlation coefficient	0,826					
Parity correlation coefficients	Y	-0,101	-0,148	0,620	0,517	-0,034
	X1		0,063	-0,119	-0,162	-0,101

	X2			-	-	-
				0,255	0,391	0,314
	X3				0,513	0,183
	X4					0,727

Given the low motivational component, which leads to the outflow of highly qualified and able-bodied people, the introduction of digital tools can reduce the shortage of personnel.

Table 9.

Results of the analysis of the multi-factor correlation-regression model of the economic activity of agricultural enterprises in the Khavast district of the Syrdarya region for 2025

Indicators	Y	X1	X2	X3	X4	X5
Error in correlation coefficients	0,026	0,131	0,131	0,093	0,111	0,124
Reliability of correlation coefficients	33,879	0,131	0,111	5,842	3,533	-1,948
Arithmetic mean	1,197	55,607	188,038	15,020	0,019	0,016
Standard quadratic deviations	0,434	192,258	134,513	6,163	0,009	0,009
Coefficients of variation, %	36,241	345,747	71,535	41,034	49,569	53,940
Regression coefficients	0,798	0,000	0,000	0,013	52,080	-52,392
Beta coefficients		-0,009	0,136	0,192	1,112	-1,067
Coefficients of determination, %	79,906	0,030	0,021	29,359	15,399	5,806
Specific detection factors	79,906	-0,016	0,198	10,383	43,630	25,710
Multiple correlation coefficient	0,894					
Parity correlation coefficients	Y	0,017	0,015	0,542	0,392	-0,241
	X1		-0,018	0,076	-0,020	-0,034
	X2			0,005	-0,119	-0,009
	X3				0,393	0,081
	X4					0,730

The variability of the resulting factor (y) is associated with the combined influence of selected factors (x1, x2) by 68.217%, including an average annual

increase in live weight of cattle by 38.419% due to changes in maintenance costs per head, and by 48.464% due to labor costs.

The study showed that livestock density has increased in the Syrdarya and Khavast districts of the Syrdarya region, which has a positive impact on the resulting indicator. The results of the analysis show that the level of digitalization of the technological process at enterprises in these regions has increased; that is, programs implemented for herd management, automation of feed distribution, and released resources serve to increase productivity.

The generalized results of the influence of factors by districts of the Syrdarya region are presented in Table 10.

In the Syrdarya and Khavast districts of the region, the main factor is the high cost of maintaining one head of livestock, as well as the high share of purchased feed due to limited pastures, meadows, and opportunities for self-production.

Table 10.

Analysis of factors that have the greatest impact on the meat productivity of cattle by districts of the Sidarya region

Regions	X1	X2	X3	X4	X5
Bayaut District	-	-	+	-	-
Akaltyn District	-	-	+	-	-
Saykhunabad district	-	-	+	+	+
Syrdarya district	+	-	+	-	-
Khavast district	+	-	+	-	-

The conducted analysis shows that there are significant differences in both production and financial results among enterprises engaged in meat cattle farming. The most efficient producers in the sector are located in the Boyovut District and Oqoltin District.

To assess the dependence of economic efficiency indicators on the scale of production, it is necessary to group cattle-fattening enterprises into appropriate categories (Table 11).

According to the research results, it can be concluded that in enterprises of the Sayxunobod District, the lowest production losses in meat livestock farming are observed in the first group, where the number of cattle does not exceed 100 heads.

Furthermore, in the conditions of the Sayxunobod District, the lowest losses are characteristic of small-scale farms, where the cost of producing 1 centner of meat is 3.6 thousand UZS lower compared to enterprises with up to 150 heads of cattle. An example of such an enterprise is the “Maqsudu Mardon” farm in

Sayxunobod district. In this farm, 120 fattening cattle were raised in 2025, and the profit from the production and sale of cattle meat amounted to 33,000 thousand UZS.

Table 11.

Economic efficiency of production in meat livestock farming in the Saykhunabad district by enterprise volume for 2018-2025

Indicators	Group of enterprises by number of livestock for rearing and feeding, head.			Total
	Up to 100	101-150	over 150	
Following	15	3	3	21
Average livestock per 1 enterprise, head.	166	120	185	100
Proportion of animals intended for breeding and fattening in the total livestock population, %	60,0	66,2	65,5	65,0
Livestock density, head per 100 hectares of agricultural land	262,0	250,3	220,2	261,8
Animal load per livestock breeder, head.	88	84	83	87
Meat production per 100 hectares of agricultural land, centners	405,8	400,5	388,9	401,0
Production cost per unit, thousand soums.	90,3	86,7	86,5	86,9
Labor costs per unit of production, man-hour	21,86	21,39	19,47	20,00
Revenue per head of livestock, thousand soums.	13,23	13,55	14,00	13,82
Profitability level of products sold, %	-23,8	-29,9	-25,0	-25,7

Conclusions and Recommendations. The conducted analysis shows that the efficiency of agricultural production, particularly meat livestock farming, is directly dependent on the optimal scale of farm enterprises and the level of

production concentration. In a market economy, determining the economically optimal size of farms requires a comprehensive consideration not only of internal production efficiency, but also of regional market capacity, price dynamics, changes in supply and demand, and other key market conditions. This necessitates a systematic and forecast-based approach to production planning.

The analysis also demonstrates that the effective development of meat livestock farming across regions depends on increasing the utilization of available natural forage resources, bringing unused land into economic circulation, and strengthening human resource capacity. In addition, insufficient development of production infrastructure—particularly the lack of modern slaughterhouses capable of processing up to 150 cattle per day and meat deep-processing facilities—remains one of the main factors limiting sector efficiency.

In this regard, the following recommendations are proposed:

- development of regional programs aimed at optimizing production concentration and forming enlarged, efficient livestock farms in meat cattle farming;
- implementation of production forecasting models at the regional level, taking into account market capacity and price dynamics;
- improvement of forage base efficiency and rational resource management systems;
- attraction of investments for the development of modern slaughtering, storage, and deep meat processing infrastructure;
- introduction of complex mechanization and gradual digitalization in the livestock sector;
- improvement of state support mechanisms based on differentiated approaches considering regional characteristics.

Overall, the implementation of these measures will contribute to increasing the competitiveness of the meat livestock sector, improving production efficiency, and ensuring stable supply of meat products to the population.

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